

Cyclic voltammetric studies of some tris(diimine)cobalt(II) complexes in dimethylformamide solution

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Abstract : The cyclic voltammetric behaviour of tris(diimine)cobalt(II) complexes, $[\text{CoL}_3]^{2+}$, (L = diimine = bipyridyl (bipy), phenanthroline (phen) and 4,7-diphenyl-1,10-phenanthroline (bathophen)) has been investigated in DMF solution containing 0.1 M NaClO₄ as a supporting electrolyte at a glassy carbon working electrode (GCE). All these complexes undergo a diffusion-controlled quasi-reversible one-electron oxidation couple ($\text{Co}^{2+/3+}$) at $E^0 = +320$ to $+430$ mV vs SCE and a single-electron reduction couple ($\text{Co}^{2+/+}$) at $E^0 = -680$ to -690 mV vs SCE. The peak current ratio for both oxidation and reduction couples is less than unity, suggesting that redox processes involve EC mechanism. CV results also revealed that the ease of reduction increases in the order : bipy \rightarrow phen \rightarrow bathophen, clearly demonstrating that the chemical nature, size and positions of the substituents on the parent phenanthroline rings, i.e., the electronic and steric characteristics of the ligands influence the redox potentials of the complexes.

Keywords : Cobalt, cyclic voltammetry, electrochemistry, phenanthrolines, redox process.

Metal complexes of the kind $(\text{ML}_n)^{n+}$, where L is either a phenanthroline (phen) or a modified phenanthroline, are particularly attractive species for developing new diagnostic and therapeutic agents that can recognize and cleave DNA¹, by virtue of their intrinsic chemical, and photochemical reactivities¹⁻³. A singular advantage in using these metallo-intercalators for such studies is that the ligand or metal in them can be varied in an easily controlled manner to facilitate an individual application, thus providing easy access for understanding details involved in DNA bonding and cleavage⁴. The biological activity of phen and substituted phen is also markedly influenced by metal complexation⁵. They exhibit numerous biological activities, e.g., antifungal, antiviral, cytotoxicity, antitumour etc.

Keeping in view the above points, we have therefore studied the cyclic voltammetric behaviour of cobalt(II) complexes with bipy, phen and bathophen in dimethyl formamide (DMF) solution. The overall aim of this work has been to correlate the electrochemical properties of these complexes with the electronic and steric characteristics of the substituted phenanthrolines.

Results and discussion

The cyclic voltammetric behaviour of some metal-chelate solutions containing Co^{II}-to-diimine ligands (1-3) in 1 : 3.5 molar ratio (diimine ligands = bipy, 1; phen, 2; and bathophen, 3) have been studied in DMF containing 0.1 M NaClO₄ at glassy carbon working electrode (GCE) with scan rate ranging

from 25 to 300 mV s⁻¹. It is noteworthy that the colours of all the freshly prepared metal-chelate solutions studied here are light orange and that low spin $3d^7$ tris(diimine)Co^{II} complex⁶, $[\text{Co}(\text{diimine})_3]^{2+}$ is formed when the ligand-to-metal ratio ≥ 3.0 .

The cyclic voltammetric data for $[\text{Co}(\text{bipy})_3]^{2+}$, $[\text{Co}(\text{phen})_3]^{2+}$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{bathophen})_3]^{2+}$ complexes are given in Table 1. All these complexes exhibit similar electrochemical behaviour. The representative cyclic voltammograms of the $[\text{Co}(\text{bipy})_3](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ complex in DMF solution to a scan rate of 25 mV s⁻¹ are displayed in Fig. 1. A positive scan started at +100 mV in the potential range from +0.80 to -1.36 V vs SCE reveals a metal-centered quasi-reversible⁷ one-electron oxidation couple $\text{Co}^{2+/3+}$ (a_1/c_1) in the positive potential region, with a formal potential, $E^0 = +415$ mV vs SCE ($E_{\text{pa}1} = +510$ mV, $E_{\text{pc}1} = +320$ mV, $\Delta E_p = 190$ mV and $I_{\text{pc}1}/I_{\text{pa}1} \approx 1.0$); a totally irreversible cathodic peak, c'_1 located at $E_{\text{pc}'1} = -330$ mV, indicating possibly the formation of a short-lived intermediate species and also a quasi-reversible one-electron reduction couple, $\text{Co}^{2+/+}$ (c_2/a_2) at a more negative potential with $E^0 = -920$ mV vs SCE ($E_{\text{pc}2} = -1010$ mV, $E_{\text{pa}2} = -830$ mV). The peak separation, ΔE_p varies as a function of scan rate. As well, the ratio of peak currents ($I_{\text{pa}2}/I_{\text{pc}2} \approx 0.46$) is less than 1.0 (Table 1), indicating that electron transfer is followed by a slow chemical reaction^{8,9} (EC mechanism). It appears that the reduction of the complex, $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}\text{L}_3]^{2+}$ results in the loss of one diimine ligand, forming a four coordinate $3d^8$ Co^I complex^{9,10}, $[\text{Co}^{\text{I}}\text{L}_2]^+$.

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammograms of $[\text{Co}(\text{bipy})_3](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ in $\text{DMF}/0.1 \text{ M NaClO}_4$ at a scan rate of 25 mV s^{-1} : (a) anodic scan, (b) cathodic scan.

On the basis of these observations it may be concluded that the following redox processes, (1) to (3) probably occur in the case of $[\text{CoL}_3]^{2+}$ complexes:

(L = diimine ligand)

It should be noted that magnitudes of the peak currents I_{pa1} and I_{pc2} differ significantly^{10,11} (Table 1), indicating that different kinds of electron-transfer processes¹² are involved in the two redox steps, (a_1/c_1 and c_2/a_2). It is noteworthy that the ligands bipy/phen/bathophen are not electro-active in the applied potential range.

Furthermore, a comparison of the reduction peak potentials (E_{pc2}) of bipy-, phen- and bathophen- Co^{II} complexes clearly shows that the ease of reduction of these complexes increases (i.e., reduction potential, E_{pc2} becomes less negative) in the order: bipy \rightarrow phen \rightarrow bathophen. This clearly demonstrates that the chemical nature, size and the position of the substituents of the phenanthroline ring influence the redox behaviour of these Co^{II} complexes. This can also be understood on the basis of overall contribution of steric and

electronic effects¹³ of the ligands. In fact there are a number of factors which affect the redox potentials^{13,14}.

Experimental

The details of electrochemical measurements have already been described⁷. All measurements were made at 30 ± 0.5 °C. 0.1 M sodium perchlorate was used as the supporting electrolyte. Glassy carbon electrode (GCE) was used as a working electrode and saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as the reference electrode ($E^0 = +240 \text{ mV}$ vs normal hydrogen electrode (NHE)). $\text{Co}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, NaClO_4 , bipy, phen and bathophen and DMF (E. Merck) were used without further purification. The metal-chelate solutions were prepared by mixing the freshly prepared deoxygenated DMF solutions of $\text{Co}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and the diimine ligands in 1 : 3.5 molar ratio. In all these experiments the concentration of cobalt(II) was $1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ for all the chelates.

The structures of the diimine ligands and tris-(diimine)cobalt(II) complexes are shown below:

Table 1. Cyclic voltammetric data for $[\text{CoL}_3](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ complexes in DMF containing 0.1 M NaClO_4

L	Scan rate/ mV s^{-1}	$E_{\text{pa1}}/$ mV	$E_{\text{pc1}}/$ mV	$I_{\text{pa1}}/$ μA	$I_{\text{pc1}}/$ μA	$E^0/$ mV	$\Delta E_p/$ mV	$\frac{I_{\text{pc1}}}{I_{\text{pa1}}}$	$E_{\text{pc1}'}/$ mV	$E_{\text{pc1}''}/$ mV	$I_{\text{pc1}'}/$ μA	$E_{\text{pc2}}/$ mV	$I_{\text{pc2}}/$ μA	$E^0/$ mV	$\Delta E_p/$ mV	$\frac{I_{\text{pc2}}}{I_{\text{pa2}}}$
bipy	25	+510	+320	1.0	1.0	+415	190	1.0	-330	-1010	4.5	-830	7.5	-920	180	0.46
	50	+520	+310	1.5	1.5	+415	210	1.0	-350	-1050	8.5	-820	12.0	-935	230	0.45
	100	+525	+295	2.0	2.0	+410	230	1.0	-375	-1070	10.0	-810	15.0	-940	260	0.40
	150	+530	+280	2.5	2.5	+405	250	1.0	-390	-1090	12.0	-800	21.0	-945	290	0.40
	200	+540	+270	3.0	3.0	+405	270	1.0	-420	-1120	13.5	-790	25.0	-955	325	0.40
	250	+545	+265	3.5	3.5	+405	280	1.0	-440	-1130	15.0	-790	27.0	-960	340	0.40
phen	300	+555	+255	3.9	3.9	+405	300	1.0	-460	-1140	16.5	-780	29.5	-960	360	0.40
	25	+480	+380	1.5	1.0	+430	100	0.66	-210	-870	2.0	-780	5.5	-825	90	0.56
	50	+500	+370	2.5	1.7	+435	130	0.66	-230	-870	2.5	-770	7.0	-820	100	0.56
	100	+510	+360	3.0	2.0	+435	150	0.66	-270	-880	3.0	-760	9.5	-820	120	0.57
	150	+520	+340	4.0	2.7	+430	180	0.66	-280	-890	4.0	-760	10.5	-825	130	0.57
	200	+530	+330	4.5	3.0	+430	200	0.66	-300	-900	5.0	-760	12.0	-830	140	0.57
bathophen	250	+540	+320	5.3	3.5	+430	220	0.66	-320	-910	6.0	-750	13.0	-830	160	0.57
	300	+550	+310	6.0	4.0	+430	240	0.66	-330	-920	7.0	-750	14.5	-835	170	0.57
	25	+370	+290	2.5	1.5	+330	80	0.63	-300	-780	3.5	-720	7.5	-750	60	0.66
	50	+380	+280	4.0	2.5	+330	100	0.63	-320	-780	4.0	-720	10.5	-750	60	0.66
	100	+400	+260	5.0	3.5	+330	140	0.63	-360	-800	5.0	-700	14.0	-750	100	0.66
	150	+420	+250	7.0	4.5	+335	170	0.63	-400	-800	5.5	-700	16.5	-750	100	0.66
	200	+430	+240	8.0	5.0	+335	190	0.63	-400	-810	6.0	-690	19.0	-750	120	0.66
	250	+440	+230	8.5	5.5	+335	210	0.63	-410	-820	6.5	-680	21.0	-750	140	0.66
	300	+450	+220	9.4	6.0	+335	230	0.63	-420	-830	7.5	-680	22.0	-755	150	0.68

$$E^0 = 1/2 (E_{\text{pa}} + E_{\text{pc}}); \Delta E_p = (E_{\text{pa}} - E_{\text{pc}})$$

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